

VETERINARY SCIENCES

CLINICAL AND THERAPEUTIC OBSERVATIONS IN PARASITIC DERMATITIS IN DOGS AND CATS

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Abstract

The investigations were conducted on 115 dogs with skin wounds and 46 cats with external otitis and was conducted through clinical examination, microscopic examination of the curetted material obtained from the skin and of the cerumen collected from the outer auditory duct. The diagnosed acarioses were treated with miticide solutions, emulsions and ointments applied daily or at 2-3 days intervals, until healing. In the generalised clinical forms, a general therapy was started with antibiotics, according to the antibiogram, immunostimulants, liver protectors, vitamin- mineral therapy and a proper feeding. The microscopic examination conducted on 115 dogs with skin wounds showed dermatitis with parasitic etiology in 58 dogs (50.4%), of which 29.3% with sarcoptic mange and 70.6% with demodicosis. Otodectic mange was noticed in 17.3% of the examined cats, of which 37.5% in Persian cats.

Keywords: sarcoptic mange, otodectes, dogs, cats, demodicosis.

INTRODUCTION

The increased incidence of parasitic dermatitis in dogs and cats produced by acari was noticed by many authors (Meleney, Nayak, Castro). In some geographical areas the sarcoptic mange is the most frequent clinical form of manifestation of dermatitis in dogs (Nayak, 1997). The zoonotic character of the sarcoptic mange was noticed in 30-50% of the children coming into contact with infested dogs and it manifested as pruritus papules on the forearms, ankle, thighs or abdomen. The otodectic mange was noticed more frequently in the cats than in dogs, the prevalence being 25% (Castro, 2005).

Demodex canis is considered to be a skin symbiont in the healthy dogs, because this species has been identified in 60% of the microscopic preparations from curetted material obtained from the skin of lesion-free dogs. The symbiotic balance is broken when factors occur which decrease the resistance of the organism, frequently the state of immunodepression (Hamman, 2004).

Demodex canis has an immunosuppressive effect, and by its irritative mechanical action it causes a hypersecretion of sebum which is favourable to the multiplication of the acari; it also has a pyogenic effect which contributes to the purulent aspect of the secretions from the wet form of the demodicosis (Hamman, 2004). The onset of demodicosis is favoured by the congenital or acquired hypoactivity of the T lymphocytes as proven by the experiments conducted on dogs used to reproduce tumours, which receive antilymphocyte serums which produce the onset of acariosis. Nayak et al. (9) reported a 60% incidence of demodicosis in puppies below the age of one year, 23% in the dogs aged 1-2 years and 17% in the dogs over 2 years.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The investigations conducted during February 2017 – April 2018 at the clinic of the Faculty of Veterinary Medicine of the Spiru Haret University, Bucharest, on a total of 115 dogs of different breeds and ages

with skin lesions and on 46 cats with external otitis. The animals have been examined clinically to determine the body regions that are affected and the aspect of the lesions.

The acari species has been identified by the microscopic examination of the preparations made from curetted material obtained from the skin and of the cerumen collected from the outer auditory duct. The microscopic preparations were cleared with sodium hydroxide 10%.

The incidence of acariosis in dogs and cats was classified according to the evolutive clinical forms by age categories and breeds. The following therapeutic designs were used to control the acariosis diagnosed in the dogs and cats:

- the dogs with sarcoptic mange were treated with doramectin, 4-5 SC administrations at 10 days, associated with a local therapy with amitraz 1%, 4-5 applications at 2-3 days;

- the local demodicosis was treated with doramectin, 3 SC administrations at 10 days, and 4-5 local applications with amitraz 1%;

- the generalised demodicosis was treated for 60-90 days by parenteral administration of doramectin, immunostimulants (Levamisol), liver protecting agents, vitamin-mineral therapy (vitamin A, biotin, Se, Zn) and antibiotics associated with local applications with amitraz 1%;

- the auricular mange in cats was treated by cleaning the outer auditory duct of the cerumen, followed by daily local instillations with one of the specific products, Oticure, Mitex or Otopguard

Results and discussion

- The incidence of the parasitic dermatitis in the group of 115 dogs: 58 dogs (50.4%) have been diagnosed with the parasitic aetiology.

- The incidence of acariosis observed in 58 dogs: 29.4% were diagnosed with sarcoptic mange and 70.6% with demodicosis

- The highest prevalence was noticed in puppies aged 1-6 months (41.1%), 11.7% in 7-11 months old puppies and in dogs aged 8-10 years, and 17.6% in 1-6 years old dogs.

The localized demodicosis was observed in 43.9% of the infested dogs, the generalized form in 24.3% of the dogs; the localised suprainfected demodicosis was

Fig 1. Demodicosis – localized simply form

observed in 4.8% of the infested dogs, while the generalised suprainfected form in 26.8% of the dogs.

The incidence of demodicosis by age category was as follows: the highest prevalence was noticed in the puppies aged 3 – 11 months (41.4%), followed by 36.5% in the dogs 1-2 years old, 17.3% in the dogs aged 3-5 years and 4.8% in the dogs aged 6-8 years

Fig 2. Demodicosis- generalized suprainfected

Fig.3. Demodicosis – localized simply form alopecia complicated

Fig 4. Demodicosis- generalized suprainfected form

CONCLUSIONS

1. Dermatitis with parasitic aetiology were reported in 50.4% of the dogs with skin lesions that were examined.
2. Sarcoptic mange was diagnosed in 29.4% and demodicosis was diagnosed in 70.6% of the dogs with ectoparasitoses;
3. 78.04% of the demodicosis cases were reported in dogs aged 3 months – 2 years;
4. 17.3% of the cats with external otitis were diagnosed with otodectic mange
5. The general and local treatment applied to the generalised wet demodicosis was 98% efficient;

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